

Academic Procrastination: Causes and Solution

Anju Rani

Research scholar ITTR, BPSMV Khanpur kalan

Corresponding author- **Anju Rani**

Email - anju.edu09@gmail.com

Introduction

Procrastination comes from the Latin “pro,” which means forward, and “crastinus,” which means of tomorrow. It is a tendency to put off, avoid or delay activities. It has also been characterized as “delaying task completion to the point of experiencing subjective discomfort”, an “intentional delay of an intended course of action” or as a stable personality trait with negative consequences. There seems to be agreement on procrastination as consistently delaying behaviors regardless of consequences.

Research has suggested, however, that procrastination is extremely common among college students. Moreover, due to the wide availability of students in a college setting, research on academic procrastination can be more easily studied. It should be noted that academic procrastination is a unique outlet for procrastination. People procrastinate on a wide variety of activities and in a wide variety of circumstances, whether it is putting off completing a project, grading papers, or leaving for a meeting. Nevertheless, unique outlets of procrastination, such as in academics, can exist where individuals tend to delay activities in certain areas. Unique outlets of procrastination have been of interest to researchers concerned in narrowing the behavioral and dependent outcomes of procrastination.

Academic Procrastination

Academic procrastination is the tendency to put off or delay school-related activities and behaviors. Academic procrastination occurs with students of all ages, whether those students are attending grade school or pursuing some type of educational attainment or degree.

Specific outlets of procrastination can be more easily studied, as well. Moreover, although it does appear that individuals have a tendency towards procrastinating or not, which in turn affects the likelihood of demonstrating procrastinator behaviors in these specific outlets, other factors can come into play which weaken this relationship. For example, individuals who do not typically procrastinate in their everyday lives may procrastinate in their academic endeavors because of a lack of understanding of the complexities of meeting numerous deadlines, inadequate beliefs regarding studying habits or because of a false belief that their high abilities allow them to do so.

Procrastination among undergraduate students in college is more common and some studies have even found that over 70% of university students admit that they procrastinate regularly. Academic procrastination occurs when students needlessly delay completing activities, projects or assignments. Such procrastination can place undue stress or anxiety upon individuals as they hasten to meet deadlines and complete assignments. Putting things off can not only affect ones psychological well-being, but can also affect ones relationship with others. As individuals fail to meet deadlines and commitments, relationships become strained. However, research is somewhat mixed on the effects of procrastination. For example, Schraw et al. (2007) argue that procrastination might have a useful adaptive advantage that allows students to

garner better use of available study time. However, other studies have established that procrastination corresponds to less success in life. The concentration of this research, like most others, is on the negative form of procrastination. Colleges have become overly reliant on predictors of academic success such as scores on the Scholastic Aptitude Test (SAT) to the point where scores on the SAT are used in extremely important selection decisions.

However, studies have shown that “procrastination is capable of accounting for variance in college grades beyond what is explainable by the SAT” (Wesley, 1994). Therefore, procrastination can possibly be distinguished as a particularly vital predictor of success in college. As a result, a valid and reliable scale of academic procrastination could be quite profitable and of great importance to colleges and universities. Such a scale can prove valuable in remediating students. Those students who exhibit higher levels of academic procrastinator tendencies could be given lessons in studying effectively and keeping deadlines and goals. If identified early enough, students can be given the right tools for overcoming procrastination and succeeding in college. Regardless of the effects of procrastination, there appears to be numerous conceptualizations and components of academic procrastination. However, several dimensions or facets of academic procrastination have been identified through past literature. Identifying those possible dimensions of academic procrastination, therefore, is one step towards the creation of a valid and reliable scale. Academic procrastination linked with perfectionism. Perfectionism depends upon some factors like:

1. Self Imposition of rather high standards.
2. Critical assessment of one’s behaviors and performance.

3. Adopting all or none principle.
4. Sale focuses on either failure or success.
5. External sources beyond internal ability.

Why do people procrastinate?

1. People procrastinate as the task they perform is unpleasant or irresistible to them. When the in hand is unpleasant, then we become reluctant to complete it or to start it. Some time we feel fear of the future. We are comfortable in our own present day. The things may be unpleasant or we may encounter some unpleasant events while doing a task. That fear also promotes procrastination.
2. Fear of the unknown what's going to happen or what you are going to encounter when talking on a particular task. Fear of change people tends to 21 resist changes. Some people are set in their ways and don't want to change their life style. They will do only those things which fascinate them and make them feel more excited and thrilled.
3. Set feasible goals extend an intimate link amid assignment actual significant goals.
4. Evaluate their own goal, strengths, weaknesses and priorities.
5. Modify their environment for that newly gained perspective.

6. Restructure activities of daily life.
7. Discipline their self to the priority them position
8. Academic procrastination is a phenomenon where students unnecessarily postpone academic assignments, like studying for a test or working on a school project. This is a common problem, which can lead to issues like worse academic outcomes and increased stress. An example of academic procrastination is a student who has a week to study for an exam, but ends up postponing their studying unnecessarily until the night before, even though they want to get started. Another example of academic procrastination is a student who delays working on an important project for an entire semester, until right before it's due. An undergraduate student who puts off studying for a test by doing unimportant chores, such as cleaning their room or baking snacks.

Characteristics of Academic Procrastination

The six characteristics of academic procrastination are psychological beliefs about abilities, distractions, social factors, time management, personal initiative and laziness. Each will be discussed briefly.

Figure 1: Characteristics of Academic Procrastination

1. Psychological Belief about Abilities

Although other studies have failed to validate the four-factor approach to active academic procrastination, studies have found that procrastinators tend to rationalize their tendencies to put things off and their ability to work under pressure. Therefore, one aspect of procrastination involves psychological beliefs about the ability to

work under pressure. This has been defined in similar studies as sensation-seeking. In other words, academic procrastinators seek, either actively or passively, to work under pressure. Those who procrastinate have an undeniable belief in their ability to work under pressure. In fact, this belief in ability might have some basis in other psychological research.

2. Distractions of Attention

One reason students tend to distract themselves with other things instead of deadlines and schoolwork stems from the fact that, typically, tasks such as projects and assignments are aversive to students. Distracting oneself from responsibilities also gives “an out” if one fails at that task. For example, if a student has an extremely difficult test or project due and is afraid of failing, he or she can protect self-worth or self-esteem by giving an outside excuse or external distracter for failing. Thus, the student instead distracts him or herself with another activity, blaming failure on said activity. Therefore, a unique characteristic of procrastinators is that they tend to immerse themselves in distractions.

3. Social Factors of Procrastination

Social factors, such as friends or family could keep one from keeping timelines or deadlines. This task aversion to school work was recognized by Brownlow and Reasinger (2000) as one of the major reasons procrastinators put off school work. Social factors can promote task aversiveness or task avoidance, both of which are dimensions of procrastination mentioned. Traditional college students are those in their early adulthood and late adolescence, aged 18-23 years of age. Such an age is characterized by social adjustment and independence. Students attempt to juggle and schedule time with family, friends and work. Add a newfound sense of independence and autonomy to this struggle and college students can turn away from school work and deadlines and choose instead to work or socialize with friends. Therefore, social factors are indicative and promotive of procrastination.

4. Time Management Skills

Time management can be defined as having an ability to consciously control activities and behaviors so as to maximize ones available time. Procrastinators tend to have an inability to manage their time and experience a wide discrepancy between their actual intent and their realized behaviors. Difficulty in managing ones time was discovered in previous studies as a reason why students academically procrastinate. Time management skills are not an inherent trait, but a learned characteristic within individuals. Time management is “a critical contributor to procrastination in academic settings”. To succeed in an academic environment, students must show up on time to classes and keep deadlines. They must also complete assignments and tests by predetermined dates.

5. Personal Initiative

Personal initiative is most synonymous to internal motivation. Therefore, it is proposed that those students who possess personal initiative and the intrinsic drive for completing their academic work

procrastinate to a lesser extent. Fear of failure, as well, could be a potential reason behind some forms of procrastination. Academic procrastinators might be prone to not carrying out tasks for fear of failing at that task. Thus, fear of failing could quite possibly be one of the reasons why students procrastinate. Students might lack initiative and have an absence of motivation and enthusiasm to complete school work because they fear failing at those tasks. Thus an academic procrastination scale must assess a student’s personal initiative.

6. Laziness

Laziness is a tendency to avoid work even when physically able. Aversiveness and laziness were factors that accounted for 18% of the variance in reasons for students’ procrastination according to Solomon and Rothblum. If students are physically avoiding school work, they are merely putting off all of this work until the end of the semester. Thus, they are exhibiting a degree of laziness and task aversiveness. According to a recent theoretical study on procrastination, up to 40% of students stated that they would drop a college course if the professor expected too much of students or was too inflexible on due dates or deadlines. Thus, academic procrastination might involve the tendency to avoid a great deal of school work, or laziness.

Prevalence of Academic Procrastination

Academic procrastination is common among students, as a large portion of them procrastinate often and to a significant degree. For example, when it comes to college students, studies show that approximately 80%–95% of college students engage in procrastination to some degree, approximately 75% consider themselves to be procrastinators, and approximately 50% say that they procrastinate in a consistent and problematic manner. Furthermore, additional studies have found procrastination in various other student populations, including those in elementary school, middle school, high school, and graduate school. In fact, procrastination is so common among students that the tendency to procrastinate on tasks until right before they are due is sometimes referred to as the student syndrome. The prevalence of academic procrastination varies based on the task involved.

Dangers of Academic Procrastination

Academic procrastination is associated with various negative effects, such as worse academic performance, worse emotional wellbeing, and worse mental and physical health. Accordingly, academic procrastination is often detrimental to those who engage in it.

Specifically, the following are the key issues that are associated with academic procrastination:

1. Worse academic performance. For example, procrastination is associated with a wide range of academic issues, like lower quality work,

- worse exam scores, worse grades, increased academic misconduct and dishonesty,
2. Worse emotional wellbeing. For example, procrastination can lead to various negative emotions, like guilt, shame, and sadness.
 3. Worse mental and physical health. For example, procrastination can lead to various mental health issues, like stress, as well as physical health issues, like lack of sleep and exhaustion.

Many of these issues are interrelated. For example, when academic procrastination leads to increased negative emotions, it can also lead to increased stress at the same time. Similarly, when academic procrastination leads to increased stress, this can, in turn, lead to issues such as exhaustion, which increases the likelihood that people will procrastinate on academic tasks, and consequently suffer from worse academic performance. In addition, the tendency to engage in procrastination is associated with a variety of issues from a career perspective, including lower salaries, shorter periods of employment, and a higher likelihood of unemployment. This can affect students who are employed while engaging in academic studies, as well as students who enter the job market after graduation.

This behavior is sometimes called “academic procrastination”. However, this term is mainly used to refer to student procrastination. Procrastination by teachers and other academics is usually more accurately categorized as a form workplace procrastination, or as a more specific form of it, like teacher procrastination and professor procrastination.

Causes of Academic Procrastination

Academic procrastination occurs when issues like anxiety and perfectionism outweigh students’ self-control and motivation. That’s why students often postpone academic tasks even when they want to get them done, and why they often only manage to start shortly before the deadline, when the increasing pressure finally pushes them to do their work.

Accordingly, there are various common internal and external causes of academic procrastination.

Internal causes of academic procrastination include the following:

1. Anxiety, for example when it comes to being anxious about studying in general. Fear of failure, for example when it comes to worrying about failing an upcoming exam.
2. Perfectionism, for example when it comes to wanting to write an essay draft without any flaws.
3. Task aversion, for example when it comes to wanting to avoid dealing with a homework assignment that’s perceived as boring.

4. Sensation seeking, for example when it comes to finding assignments more exciting to work on assignments when there’s intense time pressure.
5. Feeling overwhelmed, for example when it comes to being unsure about how to handle a large research project.
6. Physical or mental exhaustion, for example when it comes to being tired due to a demanding academic workload.
7. Lack of study or organizational skills, for example when it comes to not knowing how to set an effective study schedule.
8. Many of these issues can be attributed to negative past experiences. For example, if someone does badly in a number of course assignments, they might feel anxious when it comes to future assignments or exams in that course, which can cause them to procrastinate. However, this isn’t always the case, and lack of experience can also cause procrastination, for instance when it leads to low self-confidence. Finally, certain underlying issues can also lead to or exacerbate academic procrastination.. Similarly, issues such as low self-esteem or low self-efficacy may also lead to increased academic procrastination in some cases.

External Causes Of Academic Procrastination Include The Following:

1. Poor study environment, for example because this environment is overly loud or filled with distractions.
2. Unpleasant assignments, for example because an assignment requires students to use only a limited range of skills, which makes students more likely to perceive it as boring, and consequently more likely to be averse to it.
3. Lack of clear directions or expectations, for example because the explanation of how a paper will be graded is incomplete, vague, or ambiguous.
4. Lack of clear due dates, for example in terms of when the first draft of an essay should be submitted.
5. Lack of communication, for example in the case of an instructor not responding to a student’s requests for clarification.
6. The instructor being too lax, for example by never enforcing any deadlines in their course.
7. The instructor being too harsh, for example by providing unnecessarily unpleasant feedback on assignments.
8. External issues can sometimes lead to or exacerbate internal ones. For example, an instructor being too harsh can lead to fear of failure in a student who wouldn’t have it otherwise, or it can increase anxiety in an already anxious student.

Solutions to Academic Procrastination

Academic procrastination can be reduced by analyzing the situation, in terms of factors such as the number of students involved and the causes of their procrastination, and then implementing an appropriate solution, which consists of interventions such as intermediate deadlines, automated reminders, and self-regulation training. The subsections below contain more information on the topic. Specifically, they first outline the general types of approaches that can be used to deal with academic procrastination, and then provide examples of specific interventions and techniques that can be used as part of these approaches.

General Approaches

There are three main types of approaches for dealing with academic procrastination:

Student-led approach This involves students taking most of the responsibility for reducing their academic procrastination, with little to no external guidance. External guidance in this case might include something as minimal as a lecturer mentioning the problem of procrastination and giving students a link to a relevant guide on the topic.

Externally led approach This involves stakeholders, such as educators or administrators, using relevant anti-procrastination techniques to reduce students' procrastination, without directly discussing the issue of procrastination with the students. For example, this can involve an instructor setting a series of intermediate deadlines for all students in their course.

Joint approach This involves using both external guidance and having students take an active role in their attempts to stop procrastinating. For example, this can involve going over relevant anti-procrastination techniques with students, and helping them choose and implement their preferred ones.

None of these approaches is inherently superior to the others. Accordingly, the optimal approach in a given situation should be selected based on relevant considerations, such as effectiveness, cost, and practicality. For example, it's important to take into account the number of students that you're trying to help, since an approach that's practical when it comes to helping a single student might not be practical if you're trying to help dozens of students.

In this regard, an important factor to consider is how independent the students in question are. The more autonomy they display, the more they should generally be involved in the process of overcoming their procrastination, since this can increase their motivation and make the process more effective, while also contributing to their long-term personal growth.

“Approaches in decreasing academic procrastination found in the literature can essentially be categorized into three groups; 1. Therapeutic treatment, 2. Therapeutic prevention and 3. Instructor/teacher intervention. The first two approaches are similar in that they employ therapeutic interventions to decrease procrastination. The third approach attempts to recruit the instructor of the course to provide no therapeutic methods of decreasing procrastination tendencies among student participants.”

As such, from both a theoretical and practical perspective, if you find that you need to categorize the different types of approaches, you can do so based on the criteria that are most relevant and helpful in your particular circumstances.

Specific Techniques

Various techniques and interventions have been shown to help reduce academic procrastination. This includes, for example, teaching students motivation-regulation strategies and time management skills, or having them undergo interventions rooted in acceptance-based behavioral therapy or cognitive behavioral therapy. This also includes various educational interventions, such as regular quizzes that motivate students to study continuously rather than wait until right before final exams, automated reminders to complete assignments, and personal communication with the instructor to build a plan for avoiding late assignments. In general, it is best if the chosen anti-procrastination techniques and interventions are tailored to the specific needs of the students. However, this isn't always possible in practice, from a practical perspective; the following are general things that you can do to reduce academic procrastination:

1. Explain to students what procrastination is and what it looks like, and help them identify when they engage in it themselves. Show students why procrastination can be dangerous, when it comes to factors such as their academic performance, their career prospects, and their health.
2. Explain to students what causes procrastination, and help them identify the causes of their own procrastination. Tell students about relevant anti-procrastination techniques, some of which are listed below, Implement anti-procrastination techniques on behalf of the students, for example by breaking apart large tasks into small manageable steps. In addition, the following are some specific anti-procrastination techniques that you can use to reduce academic procrastination:
 1. Give clear directions. From the students' perspective, they can set clear goals for themselves by doing things such as deciding

where, when, and how long they plan to work on the paper.

2. Incentivize and reward progress. From the students' perspective, this can involve gamifying the studying process, for example by marking down streaks of days on which they successfully managed to achieve their study goals.
3. Find ways to make studying more enjoyable.
4. Give permission to make mistakes. Identify and resolve fear and anxieties. Figure out what students are afraid of, and resolve those fears.
5. Promote self-compassion. Self-compassion can help reduce procrastination, as well as various issues that are associated with it, such as stress.
6. Promote self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is the belief in your ability to perform the actions needed to achieve your goals, and it can help reduce procrastination.
7. Finally, there are two other important things to keep in mind when it comes to handling academic procrastination. First, most procrastinators need more than one technique in order to overcome their procrastination. Second, different techniques work better for different students in different circumstances, so just because a certain technique works well for some students, doesn't mean that it will work well for others.

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